

Nechitaylo I.S., Pidchasov Ye.V.

H.S. Skovoroda Kharkiv National Pedagogical University, Kharkiv

**SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC FACTORS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL DISTRESS
OF THE CIVILIAN POPULATION OF UKRAINE DURING THE FULL-
SCALE INVASION OF RUSSIA**

**СОЦІАЛЬНО-ДЕМОГРАФІЧНІ ЧИННИКИ ПСИХОЛОГІЧНОГО
ДИСТРЕСУ ЦИВІЛЬНОГО НАСЕЛЕННЯ УКРАЇНИ ПІД ЧАС
ПОВНОМАСШТАБНОГО ВТОРГНЕННЯ РОСІЇ**

Порушується проблематика стресових станів цивільного населення України під час повномасштабного вторгнення Росії. Зауважується, що стрес може як забезпечувати захист організму від руйнівних впливів, так і запускати механізми руйнування. Для позначення негативних ефектів стресу використовується термін «дистрес» (введений Г. Сальє). Наводяться результати дослідження, проведеного С. Дембицьким. Робляться висновки стосовно чинників, які впливають на рівень прояву психологічного дистресу. У якості таких зазначаються: кількості осіб, що спільно проживають у родині; наявність/відсутність дітей; наявність/відсутність роботи; рівень доходу; стать.

Keywords: *stress, distress, level of psychological distress, factors of psychological distress, population of Ukraine.*

Stress is a special psychophysiological state that protects the body from threatening and destructive influences. However, when a person is faced with too intense and long-lasting external influence, the body's functional countermeasures are exhausted. To describe and explain such a phenomenon, the director of the International Institute of Stress in Montreal, G. Sallie, proposed the term «distress». The scientist suggests distinguishing positive and negative functions of stress, for which he introduces the concepts of eustress (constructive stress) and distress (destructive stress). Under the influence of eustress, the maximum mobilization of the internal resources of the individual occurs. Instead, the state of distress is definitely harmful to a person (Nageishi Y., 2015; Пилипака Ю. І., Романюк В. Л., 2016, p. 78).

Ukrainian distress researcher Serhii Dembytsky notes that there are certain mediating resources that make the impact of stressors softer or harder. He notes that networks of interpersonal interactions that include an individual and are a potential resource for its support can act as such: family, friends, colleagues, neighbors, public organizations (Дембицький С. С., 2018). It should be noted that such ideas about mediative resources form the methodological basis of our scientific research, dedicated to the study of the stress state and subjective well-being of the population of the city of Kharkiv and the Kharkiv region under the conditions of Russia's invasion of Ukraine.

The war creates many significant external stimuli that trigger a whole series of distress factors. Moreover, since the war covers all citizens of the society experiencing it, the distress acquires mass characteristics. When the vast majority of the country's population is in a state of distress, it has significant negative consequences not only at the individual level, but also at the general social level. Therefore, during the war, as well as in the post-war period, the study of stressful conditions and, in particular, distress, its factors and mediative resources acquire special relevance.

S. Dembytskyi developed a test for measuring psychological distress (SCL-9-NR), which was used by the research and analytical company Factum Group as a structural part of the online survey toolkit (March-April 2022; n=485; the sample is a quota for a number of parameters of the characteristics of the urban population of Ukraine (Дембіцький С. С., 2018, 2022).

The main conclusions of the study are as follows:

- levels of psychological distress differ depending on the number of persons living together in the family. The normal level of distress is more characteristic of families of two or three people (52.3 and 47.1%). As the number of people in the family increases, the percentage of people with a high level of distress increases. Thus, in families with 6 or more people, a high level of distress was recorded in 40% of cases, despite the fact that 30% have an elevated level and 30% – normal;

- levels of psychological distress differ somewhat depending on the presence of children: respondents who do not have children are more likely to show a normal level of distress (48.3%, compared to 40.2% among those who have children);

- levels of psychological distress differ significantly depending on the availability of work. Almost half of working respondents have a normal level of distress (47.9%), while a high level is typical for 23.3%. For comparison, about 33% of unemployed respondents have a normal level of distress, and a high level is typical for 38.3%;

- it is quite expected and natural that the level of psychological distress increases depending on what share of income the respondents use for basic necessities (food, payment for housing/utilities): the larger this share is, the higher the level of psychological distress;

- levels of psychological distress differ depending on gender. The results of the study indicate that a high level of distress is more characteristic of women. Only 35.4% of women, compared to 54.5% of men, are characterized by a normal level of distress. A high level of distress was recorded in 36.5% of women and only in 16.2% of men. In addition, women are prone to greater expressiveness (persistence of manifestation) of such symptoms of distress, such as: a feeling of tension or excitement (25.1%, compared to 11.3% – in men); the feeling that feelings are easily hurt (24.7%, compared to 6.8% – in men); mild annoyance or irritation (22.8%, compared to 7.2% in men).

The results of the study allow us to conclude that certain social mediators that to some extent mitigate the impact of stressors are a small family, high income, and the presence of a job. Considering these conclusions, in the toolkit of our research, which is conducted using the online survey method and is currently at the stage of data collection, we also laid the appropriate signs that will allow us to monitor the influence of family composition, income level, and the presence of work on the state of mental health and subjective well-being of the civilian population of the Kharkiv city and the Kharkiv region.